

VECTOR SPACE APPROACH FOR MODELLING A HARTMANN WAVEFRONT SENSOR

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Abstract

This paper applies a vector space approach using matrix operations and linear algebra to develop a model of a Hartmann wavefront sensor. The wavefront sensor measures and records the wavefront phase over an aperture by dividing the total aperture into 69 subapertures. Actual wavefront sensor outputs obtained in experimental tests are analyzed to identify regions of linearity, nonlinearity, and saturation and to estimate bias and noise. Since wavefront sensor measurements can be noise-corrupted, nonlinear, and limited in accuracy, a stochastic truth model is developed which could be used to design an optimal controller to minimize the mean square phase front error.

1 Introduction

The value of receiving unobstructed optical images from an orbiting space platform or satellite is almost limitless. For maximum performance, the optical image viewed by the observation platform should have a flat wavefront in most applications. Two main error sources aberrate or induce phase error in the optical phasefront measured by a sensor. One error source is the atmosphere. The phasefront that reaches the optical mirror or sensor on the earth's surface is aberrated, caused by variations of the index of refraction due to the earth's atmosphere inhomogeneities. A second source of aberration is irregularities in the optical system. Distortions in the optical elements induce optical system phasefront errors. Compensating for these errors will "flatten out" the distorted wavefront and result in high quality imaging by the optical system.

To compensate for aberrations to the phasefront, an optical system consisting of a wavefront sensor (WFS), a deformable mirror, and a mirror controller is typically used. The wavefront sensor measures the incoming wavefront. The mirror controller utilizes this measurement information from the wavefront sensor and commands actuators on the deformable mirror to correct the aberrated wavefront. The quality of the resulting image depends upon the ability of the optical system to compensate for the distorted wavefront accurately and in a timely manner. The design of an effective controller depends upon a good model of the system's optical components. One element of the system model is the sensor model. This paper develops an accurate truth model of the wavefront sensor component of the optical system.

The wavefront sensor measures and records the phasefront or contour over an aperture. The wavefront is a continuous function in three dimensions (x, y, t), while the wavefront sensor performs a discrete sampling of this function. One concern with the wavefront sensor is that it requires a significant computational overhead which acts as a time delay to the system. The WFS must be accurately modelled to minimize any adverse effects of this time delay and any other sensor errors. Frequency response data for the WFS was used to measure the time delay of the sensor. Static outputs of the wavefront sensor were used to identify regions of linearity, nonlinearity, and saturation and to estimate bias and noise levels.

2 Hartmann Sensor

The Hartmann wavefront sensor consists of a two-dimensional array of lenslets which focus an incoming wavefront onto an optical detector array. The lenslet array divides the aperture into subapertures, each containing a focused spot of a wavefront segment. The wavefront sensor measures the spot location within each subaperture, with each spot location representing the gradients of the wavefront in the x and y directions (referred to as the x -tilt and y -tilt of the wave-

front). The Hartmann WFS then generates a phase reconstruction of the wavefront from the gradient measurements. The wavefront phase information is then processed by a digital-to-analog (D/A) converter to provide analog outputs for use by an analog input device. The Hartmann wavefront sensor can be broken into the following units: a monolithic lenslet module or array (MLM), a front end detector (FRED) containing a Reticon array optical sensor, a digitizer, and a programmable microcoded processor (PMP) (Figure 1).

The monolithic lenslet module (MLM) is the first element of the wavefront sensor. The MLM divides the incoming aberrated wavefront and focuses it on the WFS Reticon array optical sensor. The MLM consists of a single sheet of square lenslets stamped in a 13×13 array with each lenslet 600 micrometers per side. The outer two lenslet bands of the MLM provide a guard band leaving a 9×9 array of active lenslets. Three lenslets from each corner are disregarded, leaving 69 lenslets to focus the wavefront on the optical sensor at 69 points (subapertures). The MLM is positioned in front of the Reticon optical sensor at a focal length of 72 millimeters. The subaperture spot size is determined by [1]:

$$r = \frac{2\lambda f}{a} \quad (1)$$

where r = spot diameter, λ = light wavelength, f = focal length, and a = lenslet aperture size.

The lenslet actually focuses a diffraction pattern and not just a circular spot of light. The diffraction pattern for a square aperture consists of a center spot of intense light and a pattern of much weaker two-dimensional orthogonal light bands aligned with the aperture's two-dimensional axes [1]. Because of their symmetry and lower intensity light, these side bands normally offset each other and are insignificant in the calculation of the main spot's center. As the main spot nears the edge of the subaperture, the symmetry disappears as one side of the light bands moves off the subaperture and into the guard band area and is not included as an offset to the other side in the calculations of the main spot's center. However, because the light intensity of the side bands is much weaker than the main spot's light intensity, the contribution from the side bands remains insignificant until the main spot location reaches saturation. Once the main spot passes the saturation point, the side bands begin to offset the principal spot's location back towards the subaperture center, even as the main spot moves farther to the edge of the subaperture.

The front end detector (FRED) is the second element of the wavefront sensor. Its purpose is to sense the light intensity pattern and provide an analog output for processing. The key component of the FRED is its optical sensing element; a Reticon chip. The Reticon contains an array of 100,000 photodiode pixels (100 rows by 100 columns). Each photodiode pixel outputs an analog value corresponding to the illumination it senses during a sample period. The pixels are spaced 60 micrometers center-to-center in both the x and y directions. Each subaperture is sensed by a 5×5 pixel array of the Reticon. Also, between each subaperture there are five rows or columns of guard pixels. Thus the 9×9 array of subapertures employs an 85×85 array of the Reticon. The remaining 15 pixels in each direction (ten pixels on the top and one side, five pixels on the bottom and other side), provide a guard band frame. Each lenslet is centered over a 25 pixel subaperture. The guard pixels help eliminate ambiguity because a spot that moves off a subaperture moves into a guard band area instead of another subaperture. It takes approximately seven milliseconds to record the analog values at all 100,000 pixels of the Reticon resulting in a wavefront sampling rate of 140 hertz.

The digitizer is the third element of the wavefront sensor. It is an A/D converter that transforms the analog voltage outputs from the Reticon's pixels to 12 bit digital words for the PMP. The digitizer is important because it limits to 12 significant bits the precision of the data processed by the PMP, which operates internally with 16 bit resolution.

The fourth and most complex element of the wavefront sensor is the programmable microcoded processor. The PMP is a collection of processor boards that perform the wavefront calculations and supply the wavefront sensor outputs. The first function of the PMP is to determine the slope or gradient of the wavefront at each subaperture about both the x and y directions (x-tilts and y-tilts). This is accomplished with the tilt processor using a centroid algorithm or weighted pixel averaging. The tilt processor applies weighted pixel averaging to the 25 pixel values in each subaperture to determine the MLM focused spot position. After averaging is completed, each spot location is passed from the tilt processor as a vector pair of 16 bit two's complement values representing the wavefront gradients at that subaperture.

The second function of the PMP is to reconstruct the wavefront from the measured x-tilts and y-tilts, performed by the phase reconstructor. The reconstructor takes the vector pairs data from the tilt processor and applies an extensive software routine involving matrix operations. The result is a digital representation of the wavefront phase at each subaperture.

The last function of the PMP is to provide the analog outputs of the Wavefront sensor. The D/A converter takes the reconstructed wavefront phase data at each subaperture and converts the internal digital PMP units to an analog voltage output. The D/A converter output range is ± 10 volts peak-to-peak. The 69 analog outputs of the wavefront sensor are then used as inputs for a deformable mirror controller.

The A/D converter is the interface to the deformable mirror controller. Because the wavefront sensor was directly connected to the controller on the optical bench, it was not possible to obtain directly the analog outputs of the Hartmann wavefront sensor for analysis. The A/D converter was used to provide a sampled WFS output for analysis.

With the lenslets centered over the subapertures, a "flat" wavefront normal to the lenslet results in a spot of light in the center of each subaperture. Aberrations or tilts in the wavefront cause the light spot to shift away from the subaperture's center. The difficult task of determining a wavefront's gradients (tilts) can be accomplished by finding the spot's location within the subaperture pixel array. Weighted pixel averaging calculates the spot's subaperture position, where the spot's position is referenced to the center of the spot [2]. During a sample period, each pixel in the subaperture measures the light intensity sensed over its area. This measured value is used as a discrete number at the center of the pixel. Figure 2 depicts the 25 pixels of a subaperture arranged in an array of $i = 1$ to 5 rows and $j = 1$ to 5 columns. To calculate the spot location in the x-axis direction (y-tilt), the pixel values in each column are summed. Then each column value is multiplied by its weighting coefficient, and the weighted column values are summed. Last, this weighted sum is normalized (divide by the sum of all the pixel values). From Equation 2, y-tilt (x-axis coordinate) is calculated as the sum of the weighted columns divided by the sum of the nonweighted columns:

$$y - \text{tilt} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^5 c_j (\sum_{i=1}^5 p_{i,j})}{\sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 p_{i,j}} \quad (2)$$

where $p_{i,j}$ = pixel(i,j) and c_j = weighting coefficient for jth column.

Repeating the same process along the rows, x-tilt is calculated as the sum of the weighted rows divided by the sum of the nonweighted rows:

$$x - \text{tilt} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^5 b_i (\sum_{j=1}^5 p_{i,j})}{\sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 p_{i,j}} \quad (3)$$

where b_i = weighting coefficient for ith row.

The Hartmann wavefront sensor is able to reconstruct the wavefront phases from the measured x-tilts and y-tilts. This is performed by the phase reconstructor using an extensive software routine involving matrix operations. The result is a digital representation of the wavefront phase at each subaperture.

As tilt is applied to the Hartmann wavefront sensor, the spot moves away from the subaperture center linearly. Locating the spot with weighted pixel averaging maintains this linear displacement until the leading edge of the spot reaches the edge of the subaperture. At this point, for each incremental displacement away from the subaperture center, weighted pixel averaging adds less than an incremental displacement to the spot's location. The spot's calculated position moves slightly back toward the subaperture center as the actual spot center moves past the subaperture edge. Tilt saturation occurs between the center and outer edge of the subaperture's edge pixel, closer to the subaperture edge. A nonlinear tilt response starts to appear as the leading edge of the spot passes the subaperture's outer edge, which corresponds to the spot center passing the subaperture edge pixel's inner edge.

3 Vector Space Analysis

The optical wavefront that enters a wavefront sensor can be represented as a continuous phase function $\phi(x, y)$ in a two dimensional space. The function $\phi(x, y)$ can be visualized as a surface contour at the wavefront sensor aperture, where the amount of displacement of any point on the surface contour from the aperture's x-y plane represents a phase difference from some arbitrary reference value. The phase function $\phi(x, y)$ can be expressed as a linear combination of orthogonal basis functions:

$$\phi(x, y) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} a_i f_i(x, y) \quad (4)$$

where each $f_i(x, y)$ is an orthogonal basis function set multiplied by a scalar factor a_i . The continuous phase function $\phi(x, y)$ is measured by the wavefront sensor at a discrete set of points (69 points for the Hartmann WFS). The discrete sampled output of the wavefront sensor is available in the form:

$$\phi_{jk} = \phi(x_j, y_k) \quad (5)$$

where j and k are indices representing the discrete measurement points on the aperture.

The continuous phase function $\phi(x, y)$ that represents the input to the wavefront sensor can be approximated by the discrete measurements of the wavefront sensor. The accuracy of the approximation will be satisfactory if the number of sample points is sufficiently large with respect to the inverse of the function's highest frequency.

From an aperture that is measured at n discrete points, an n-dimensional column vector V can be formed from the sampled measurements:

$$V = [\phi_{11}, \phi_{12}, \dots, \phi_{jk}]^T \quad (6)$$

This measurement vector V lies in the real n-dimensional vector space R^n . If the continuous phase function is sampled at discrete points, it can be represented by a measurement vector, in an n-dimensional vector space. The vector V can then be expressed as a linear combination of vector functions. The dimension of the vector space equals the number of discrete sample or measurement points.

The Hartmann wavefront sensor discretely samples the x-tilt and y-tilt of the input phase function. This suggests the following expansion of Equation 4:

$$\phi(x, y) = a_{xt} f_{xt}(x, y) + a_{yt} f_{yt}(x, y) + a_{hot} f_{hot}(x, y) \quad (7)$$

where $f_{xt}(x, y)$ is a basis function describing x-tilt, $f_{yt}(x, y)$ is a basis function describing y-tilt, $f_{hot}(x, y)$ is a basis function describing all higher order terms, and a_{xt}, a_{yt}, a_{hot} are corresponding scale factors.

Notice that

$$a_{hot}f_{hot} = \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} a_i f_i(x, y) \quad (8)$$

which represents a linear combination of all orthogonal basis function sets except for $a_{xt}f_{xt}(x, y)$ ($i = 0$) and $a_{yt}f_{yt}(x, y)$ ($i = 1$).

Discretizing Equation 7 and substituting it in Equation 6, the measurement vector V is expanded as follows:

$$V = a_{xt}f_{xt}(x_j, y_k) + a_{yt}f_{yt}(x_j, y_k) + a_{hot}f_{hot}(x_j, y_k) \quad (9)$$

Define the sampled basis vector function as $X_i = f_i(x_j, y_k)$. Then the measurement vector V is clearly defined as a vector sum of orthogonal vectors. Equation 9 provides a vector representation of the measured phase function from the wavefront sensor. Provided the x-tilt and y-tilt vector functions have been defined, Equation 9 involves the tilt magnitude in the x-tilt vector direction (a_{xt}), the tilt magnitude in the y-tilt vector direction (a_{yt}), and the magnitude and vector direction (f_{hot}) of the higher order terms (composed of noise, bias, aberration and other phase front errors). To represent the measurement vector V uniquely, the vector functions must be linearly independent, forming a basis vector set for an m -dimensional subspace ($m = 3$ in this case) of the n -dimensional vector space. Linear independence is satisfied if the vectors are orthogonal. Additionally, the scale factors are physically significant if the vector functions are required to have unit norm. Therefore Equation 9 is most useful when the vector functions form an orthonormal basis [5]. Given any set of linearly independent vectors, an orthonormal set can be constructed by using the Gram-Schmidt process [3].

The Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process is the heart of the vector analysis approach to the wavefront sensor. A two-step process is used to construct an orthonormal vector set from any spanning set of linearly independent vectors. The first step is to use the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process to construct an orthogonal vector set. The second step is to normalize each vector of the orthogonal vector set. Using the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization process, the measurement vector defined in Equation 9 can now be expressed as a linear combination of scaled unit vector functions:

$$V = a_{xt}U_{xt} + a_{yt}U_{yt} + a_{hot}U_{hot} \quad (10)$$

where U_{xt} , U_{yt} , U_{hot} are x-tilt, y-tilt, and higher order term orthonormal vector directions respectively. a_{hot} is the scalar magnitude representing the magnitude of aberrations in the wavefront from all error sources. Once proper orthonormal vector functions are determined for the x-tilt and y-tilt directions, vector analysis can be applied to the wavefront sensor measurement vector V . The results of the analysis are available in the form of the calculations of the scalar magnitudes of the unit vectors.

Before vector analysis can be performed on the wavefront sensor, the orthonormal vector functions U_{xt} and U_{yt} must be determined. First, vector functions must be found that are physically meaningful. Then the Gram-Schmidt process is applied to construct an orthonormal vector set. A representation for the orthonormal vector U_{hot} does not need to be developed. Once the resultant vector $a_{hot}U_{hot}$ is calculated, only the scalar magnitude a_{hot} is needed for analysis. The Hartmann wavefront sensor discretely samples the x-tilt and y-tilt of the input phase function. This suggests a need to develop two physically significant vector functions to model the x-tilt and y-tilt. The measurements taken at the aperture are available as two data points, x-tilt and y-tilt, at each subaperture. The Hartmann wavefront sensor reconstructs these aperture measurements to output a phase representation of the input wave. This information is available as single data values, corresponding to each subaperture, that represent the effect of the input wavefront's measured x-tilt and y-tilt. Since both types of data sets are analyzed, two sets of orthonormal vectors representing the x-tilt and y-tilt need to be developed.

Once the orthonormal vectors are developed, vector analysis of a measurement vector can be performed. Using vector projection, the measurement vector can be expressed as in Equation 9. The analysis results in the unit vector magnitudes a_{xt} , a_{yt} , and a_{hot} .

4 Results

Using the vector space approach developed, the operation of the Hartmann wavefront sensor can be analyzed. Figure 3 displays a block diagram of the functions and available internal and external outputs of the Hartmann wavefront sensor's PMP. The three types of data available for analysis, which represent the input wavefront at different stages of wavefront sensor processing, are identified as VECTOR data, RECON data, and D2A data (see Figure 3). The VECTOR data contains 138 data points consisting of two data points for each subaperture. The data pairs at each subaperture are the x and y coordinates of the spot in the subaperture. The first data value of the pair is the x-coordinate which measures the y-tilt. The second data value of the pair is the y-coordinate which represents the x-tilt. The RECON data contains 69 data points, consisting of one data point per subaperture measuring the wavefront phase at each subaperture. The 69 D2A data values also measure the wavefront phase at each subaperture. Only data from the 69 active subapertures are used in the vector analysis.

The orthonormal vectors required for the analysis of the Hartmann wavefront sensor have been discussed earlier. For analysis of the VECTOR data, the following orthogonal vectors are used for x- and y-tilt vectors.

$$X_{xt} = [0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, \dots, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1]^T \quad (11)$$

$$X_{yt} = [1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0]^T \quad (12)$$

The orthogonal vectors X_{xt} and X_{yt} each have 138 data points consisting of alternating ones and zeros. To build an orthonormal basis vector set, these vectors are divided by their respective norms. The norm of each vector is $\sqrt{69}$. Dividing each vector by its norm, the following orthonormal vector function set is determined for the VECTOR data:

$$U_{xt} = (1/\sqrt{69})[0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, \dots, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1]^T \quad (13)$$

$$U_{yt} = (1/\sqrt{69})[1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0]^T \quad (14)$$

For analysis of the RECON and D2A data, the orthogonal vectors developed for 69 subapertures are

$$\begin{aligned} X_{xt} = & [4, 4, 4, 4, 4, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 3, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2, \\ & 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, -1, -1, -1, -1, \\ & -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, -2, -2, -2, -2, -2, -2, -2, -2, \\ & -3, -3, -3, -3, -3, -3, -3, -4, -4, -4, -4, -4]^T \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} X_{yt} = & [-2, -1, 0, 1, 2, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, \\ & 1, 2, 3, 4, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, -4, -3, -2, -1, \\ & 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, -4, -3, -2, \\ & -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2]^T \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

To build an orthonormal basis vector set, these vectors are divided by their norms. The norm of each vector is $\sqrt{376}$. Dividing each vector by its norm yields the orthonormal vector functions U_{xt} and U_{yt} .

In addition to the three data test sets, frequency response plots of the Hartmann wavefront sensor were taken to indicate the time delay of the system. The plots show the wavefront sensor output remained relatively constant at low frequencies, starting to degrade with an input signal between 48 to 60 Hertz. A large loss occurs near 140 Hertz, corresponding to the sampling rate of the Reticon chip. The plots are provided in Figure 4.

The vector analysis was performed on VECTOR, RECON, and D2A test data sets. The resulting scalars a_{xt} , a_{yt} , and a_{hot} , are tabulated for the VECTOR data only. The last column is the a_{hot} term magnitude with bias subtracted. The first a_{hot} term in the table (a zero tilt value) is used to compute the bias. The time data is identified as VECTOR followed by a 0 through 14 for 0 through 140

minutes. The tilt data is identified as TECTOR followed by a 0 through 5 or M for y-tilt or by 1X through 5X or MX for x-tilt. The 0 through 5 or M refer to the tilt scale of 0 through 50 units or maximum tilt. With the tables are figures containing plots of the scalars as a function of time, y-tilt, or x-tilt. On each plot, a_{xt} is plotted as a solid line, a_{yt} is plotted as a dotted line, and a_{hot} is plotted as a dashed line.

Figures 5, 6, and 7 show that drift occurs during the first 40 to 60 minutes and slows somewhat afterwards. Assuming 0.9 wavelengths per pixel and 2.2 pixels for maximum tilt, maximum tilt occurs at approximately two wavelengths of tilt. For the VECTOR scalars, a_{yt} has a drift range of approximately 292 units compared to 13489 units for two wavelengths of tilt (maximum tilt), or a drift equal to 0.043 wavelengths per wavelength of subaperture tilt. Similarly, a_{xt} has a drift equal to 0.043 wavelengths. For a subaperture dynamic range of 4 wavelengths, these scalars indicate a one percent error caused by the drift. The a_{hot} component of the measurement vector barely drifts with time once y-tilt and x-tilt are removed. This is supported by the last column of Table 1. The drift error calculation is based on the data extremes for the entire test period. The data suggests the drift rate is less than one percent after the Hartmann WFS reaches steady state (warms up).

Figure 5 shows the y-tilt performance of the VECTOR data while Figure 6 presents the x-tilt performance of the data. Readily apparent on the y-tilt figure is the linearity of the a_{yt} response as y-tilt is increased. Also, the a_{xt} response remains relatively constant and near zero over the y-tilt range. The a_{hot} response (dashed line) also remains relatively constant and near zero over the y-tilt range, although displaced more from zero than a_{xt} . Similar results occur on the x-tilt figure. Table 3 presents the average a_{xt} and a_{hot} magnitude for comparison with the maximum a_{yt} tilt magnitude. Similarly, Table 4 displays the average a_{yt} and a_{hot} magnitude for comparison with the maximum a_{xt} tilt magnitude occurring at two wavelengths of x-tilt. Under perfect conditions, the average values in Tables 3 and 4 would remain zero as tilt is applied. Table 5 displays the average value magnitudes compared to the maximum tilt magnitudes (occurring at two wavelengths of tilt) to determine the error in terms of wavelength.

As an example of an entry for Table 5, using data from Table 4:

$$a_{yt}error = (75.5/15126.8) * 2\lambda = 0.010\lambda \quad (17)$$

Using a dynamic range of four wavelengths for the subaperture, the a_{hot} component of the measurement vector, which includes the effects of noise, bias, and nonlinearity, shows an error between 0.75 and 1.0 percent (based on the D2A and RECON values of a_{hot}).

5 Summary

This paper applied a vector space approach to analyze a Hartmann wavefront sensor. In applying the analysis tools to data available, the outputs from the wavefront sensor show excellent linearity in response to the input wavefront tilts. The resultant scalar that includes the effects of noise, bias, and nonlinearity, a_{hot} , displayed an error range between 0.75 and 1.0 percent. In addition, the Hartmann wavefront sensor shows an error between 0.5 and 1.0 percent due to drift over time. Relating these errors to the ± 10 volts outputs of the D/A converter, a total error in the range of 1.25 to 2.0 percent can be expected. Since the D/A output range is ± 10 volts, this equates to an error at the D/A outputs of 125 to 200 millivolts. Based on discussions with the Hartmann wavefront sensor operators, the expected results of the analysis were for approximately 150 mV error at the D/A converter. It was suspected that the D/A converter is an excessively noisy component of the Hartmann wavefront sensor, contributing a large portion of the total error. The analysis didn't show this. If scaling is ignored, the error at the D/A appears eight times larger than the error at the reconstructor. Although this research was aimed specifically at the Hartmann wavefront sensor, the vector space approach developed can be applied to analyze any wavefront

sensor. Details of the research presented here can be found in [4].

Using the results in this paper one can readily develop a stochastic measurement model of the form

$$z = Hx + v \quad (18)$$

where x is a state vector selected by the designer, and v is a vector of white noise terms whose strengths and variances can be established based upon the noise characteristics presented in this paper. A discussion of how to do this is found in [3].

References

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Figure 1 Wavefront Sensor

Figure 2 Subaperture Pixel Mapping

Figure 3 Programmable Microcoded Processor

Figure 5 VECTOR scalars vs. Time

Figure 4 WFS Frequency Response

Figure 6 VECTOR Scalars vs. Y-Tilt

Figure 7 VECTOR Scalars vs. X-Tilt

FILE	A_Y	A_X	A_{HOT}	$A_{HOT}-BIAS$
VECTOR0	852.6	785.6	902.5	0.0
VECTOR1	842.8	744.2	871.8	-30.7
VECTOR2	839.6	689.6	859.9	-42.6
VECTOR3	978.6	617.2	910.7	8.2
VECTOR4	928.3	490.9	905.2	2.7
VECTOR5	952.3	531.1	881.1	-21.4
VECTOR6	1047.8	493.0	936.8	34.3
VECTOR7	1050.9	484.3	908.2	5.7
VECTOR8	1040.5	469.5	906.2	3.7
VECTOR9	1051.6	473.8	906.6	4.1
VECTOR10	1110.7	473.0	935.0	32.5
VECTOR11	1121.3	459.8	947.1	44.6
VECTOR12	1131.8	456.6	941.9	39.4
VECTOR13	1070.0	506.2	914.3	11.8
VECTOR14	1113.5	486.5	935.6	33.1

Table 1 Time Data - VECTOR Source

Data Set	Maximum a_y Tilt Value ²	Average a_x Value	Average a_{hot} Value
VECTOR	13488.9	165.0	995.4
RECON	15688.7	111.3	309.2
D2A	125256.6	1089.3	2596.5

Table 3 Y-Tilt Comparison

FILE	A_Y	A_X	A_{HOT}	$A_{HOT}-BIAS$
TECTOR0	-97.9	78.7	997.3	0.0
TECTOR1	-994.4	212.8	1027.4	31.1
TECTOR2	-1897.0	237.4	1017.1	19.8
TECTOR3	-3115.0	210.4	984.2	-13.1
TECTOR4	-4255.3	223.4	1028.1	30.8
TECTOR5	-5241.2	124.5	1138.8	141.5
TECTORM	-13488.9	67.7	775.0	-222.3
TECTOR1X	-147.7	873.6	1007.9	10.6
TECTOR2X	-110.7	2118.4	925.5	-71.8
TECTOR3X	-76.6	3161.3	940.5	-56.8
TECTOR4X	-66.7	4140.7	927.4	-69.9
TECTOR5X	-93.1	5349.2	945.1	-52.2
TECTORMX	63.9	15126.8	990.0	-7.3

Table 2 Tilt Data - VECTOR Source

Data Set	Maximum a Tilt Value ^x	Average a_y Value	Average a_{hot} Value
VECTOR	15126.8	75.5	962.0
RECON	17590.5	34.4	259.3
D2A	140518.9	313.0	2107.7

Table 4 X-Tilt Comparison

Data Set	Y-Tilt		X-Tilt	
	A_x Error	a_{hot} Error	a_y Error	a_{hot} Error
VECTOR	0.024	0.148	0.010	0.127
RECON	0.014	0.039	0.004	0.029
D2A	0.017	0.041	0.002	0.030

Table 5 Scalar Errors vs. Data